

INVESTIGATION OF DAMAGE ACCUMULATION IN GLASS/CARBON FIBER HYBRID COMPOSITES THROUGH ACOUSTIC EMISSION METHOD

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ABSTRACT

In this study glass/carbon fiber hybrid laminates are produced with different stacking sequence. Tensile and flexural test specimens are prepared and acoustic emission (AE) is used for damage classification during mechanical tests. The calculation of the hybrid effect for flexural and tensile specimen shows the significant influence of stacking sequence on hybrid effect under flexural loads while it has very little effect on tensile properties. The damage evolution is monitored by AE signals and damage types are identified by clustering the AE hits based on their weighted peak frequency and partial power using K-means method. While tensile specimens revealed four clusters of AE hits, flexural samples showed three classes of damage. The missing cluster under flexural loads is related to identified to be fiber pull out, which is a rare failure type under flexural loading. The spectrograms obtained for AE hits showed that different sources of AE hits result in the distinct frequency-time structure of waveform. It is revealed that the distribution of energy over time and frequency domain is directly related to the type of material(s) involved during the development of the damage. Results of the frequency-time analysis showed that the peaks of energy released during acoustic emission bursts are related to the stiffness of the material being damaged.

1 DAMAGE ACCUMULATION IN HYBRID FIBER LAMINATES

Fiber reinforced polymer composites are the prior choice for several engineering applications specifically in aerospace and transportation industries. The interest to use FRPs is mainly due to high strength, low density and anisotropic properties of these materials. These advantages are accompanied by a relatively big drawback, low fracture toughness, which becomes even bolder for carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) laminates. Therefore, preventing crack initiation and growth in CFRP laminates becomes a very important factor for designing light composite structures. Various investigations have been focused to address this problem through impregnation of laminates with nanomaterials and self-healing agents[1-3]. Several other researchers have utilized 3D printing technology to increase mechanical behavior of CFRP laminates [4-6]. Although these approaches represent improved results, they still need major modifications before being available as a key manufacturing method [7]. Fiber hybridization is another method to increase the ductility of low elongation composites such as CFRP with high elongation fibers like glass fiber reinforced polymers (GFRPs). Implementing this scheme helps to use the high strength of CFRPs and high elongation of GFRPs at hybrid fiber system. The main outcome of this fiber hybridization is called *Hybrid Effect* which can be defined as Equation (1):

$$\% \text{ Hybrid Effect} = 100 \times (\varepsilon_{f-HYB} - \varepsilon_{f-LE}) / \varepsilon_{f-LE} \quad (1)$$

where ε_{f-HYB} is the strain corresponding to the initial stress drop in the stress-strain curve of hybrid composite and ε_{f-LE} is the ultimate failure strain of low elongation laminate, respectively. Thus, glass/carbon fiber hybrid laminates show higher strength and larger apparent failure strain in contrast to GFRPs and CFRPs respectively. Various aspects are involved in the resultant hybrid effect such as difference of average failure strain for low elongation and high elongation fibers, the amount of low elongation fiber compared to high elongation ones, degree of dispersion of fibers and strength distribution of fibers, interlocking of weaving fibers, chemical treatment of fibers and strain rate[8-15]. Recent advances in hybrid fiber laminates have revealed that using very thin layers of low elongation fiber laminae between high elongation plies can reduce the possibility of a global failure of samples immediately after initial failure at low elongation ply. [16-18]. This effect is obtained by hindering interlaminar delamination after the initial failure of low elongation plies, thus the load is transferred to high elongation layers and materials integrity is preserved. As seen, it is very crucial to analyze the damage evolution in hybrid fiber reinforced laminates under various loading conditions and provide a concrete knowledge regarding failure development in these materials.

One of the useful methods to monitor damage evolution in composite structures is acoustic emission analysis. Acoustic emission waves are elastic waves which are released due to a burst of energies (hits) as the damages initiate and/or grow inside materials. These acoustic waves can be recorded with the help of piezoelectric sensors attached to the surface of materials and provide very valuable data regarding the initiation and growth of damages[19]. Since these energy bursts inside material have waveforms, so they possess specific features of the waves in time and frequency domain. This fact helps to attribute a vector to each acoustic waveform and distinguish between each individual acoustic signal based on values of its features, i.e. elements of the vector[20]. The intriguing point of this approach is that the damages due to similar failure types presumably possess alike feature values, therefore damages can be clustered (classified) through pattern recognition methods in multidimensional vector space. Several algorithms can be used for clustering data such as principal component analysis (PCA), K-medoids, Density-based clustering (DBSCAN), K-means, etc.

Clustering acoustic emission data is even more useful for analysis of damage evolution inside hybrid fiber composite materials as there are different failure types happening simultaneously inside various ply types. Some investigations have shown that the clustering based on frequency and amplitude values can distinguish between three main failure types inside fiber reinforced laminates, i.e. matrix cracking, interface failure and fiber breakage[19, 21, 22]. On the other hand, researchers have also conducted more elaborate studies and showed 5 clusters related to matrix cracking, delamination, debonding, fiber breakage and fiber pull out based on peak frequency ranges [23]. Very handful of investigations have used acoustic emission for damage analysis in hybrid fiber reinforced laminates. Saidane et al. has identified four distinct clusters in hybrid flax/glass fiber reinforced laminates corresponding to matrix cracking, interface failure, delamination and fiber breakage[24]. In another study Fotouhi et al. defined two clusters namely delamination and fragmentation for thin carbon ply UD glass/carbon hybrid laminates, their research was trying to characterize the damage development in the pseudo-ductile region of thin ply hybrid laminates[25]. Investigative overview of literature about hybrid fiber laminates shows that no specific study has monitored damages in these laminates through acoustic emission approach followed by frequency-time structure analysis. Moreover, no study is focused on distinguishing the type of damages occurring in the various hybrid configuration under various loading condition.

The present study focuses on damage analysis in glass/carbon fiber hybrid laminates with various stacking sequences under tensile and flexural loading conditions. For the first time, acoustic emission has been used to distinguish various damages occurring inside glass/carbon fiber hybrid composites with

different stacking sequences. Comparison of acoustic emission results for flexural and tensile tests has revealed four clusters of acoustic emission signals attributed to four damage types in these laminates. It is shown that the presence of a unique range of a cluster under tensile loading condition can be attributed to fiber pull out. The results of clustering are consolidated through spectrogram analysis of sample acoustic emission hits from each cluster. Moreover, a certain configuration of glass/carbon fiber hybrid laminate has revealed higher strength compared to CFRP laminate, this behavior is attributed to residual thermal stress present inside the hybrid laminates.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 MANUFACTURING HYBRID LAMINATES

Unidirectional glass and carbon fabric were used with properties indicated in Table 1. The dry glass and carbon fibers were cut with the size of 60×30 cm and stacked as [C/C/C]_s, [C/G/G]_s, [G/C/G]_s, [G/G/C]_s and [C/G/C]_s on a heating table used as the mold for vacuum assisted resin transfer molding method (VARTM). These configurations were named as AC, 1C, 2C, 3C and 13C respectively for convenience. Matrix material used for the manufacturing process consists of Araldite LY 564 resin and Hardener XB 3403. Before impregnation of dry fibers with the degassed epoxy and hardener mixture, complete sealing and vacuum are employed over the stacked dry fibers. After infusion of the matrix material into the fibers, the curing process is conducted at 80 °C for 48 hours. Properties of each produced laminate are obtained as seen in table 2.

Fabric	Fiber Type	Areal Weight (g/cm ²)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)
UD Glass	L300 E10B-0 Metyx	330	80
UD Carbon	12K A-42 AKSACA	300	240

Table 1 : Properties of used fibers

Laminate	Density(g/cm ³)	Volume Fraction of Carbon Fiber [%]	Volume Fraction of Glass Fiber [%]	Thickness (mm)
1C	1.50	21	25	1.70
2C	1.64	23	28	1.69
3C	1.59	22	27	1.68
13C	1.49	42	13	1.61

Table 2 : Physical properties of manufactured hybrid laminates

2.2 MECHANICAL TESTS AND ACOUSTIC EMISSION MONITORING

Tensile specimens were cut according to ASTM D3039 with the size of 250× 20×1.7mm. Aluminum tabs with the size of 50× 20×1.5mm adhered to two ends of tensile samples. For bending tests, 6 V-notch samples were cut according to ASTM D790 standard with the size of 80× 15×1.7mm. All mechanical tests were performed with a test speed of 2mm/min according to standards. To obtain the strain values from tensile tests, strain gauges adhered at mid-point of gauge length of tensile samples as shown in Figure 1 (striped pattern rectangle). Displacement data for flexural tests were obtained through a built-in linear variable differential transformer (LVDT) system of universal test machine and then converted to strain according to ASTM D790. The failure strains of each laminate are used to calculate the hybrid effect values under various loading types, i.e. tensile and flexural.

To monitor the acoustic emission activity two piezoelectric sensors were mounted linearly on the surface of the samples with a distance of 60mm from each other as depicted in black color in Figure 1. Data acquisition parameters for acoustic emission hardware were set manually to 45dB as the threshold, 50 μs for peak definition time (PDT), 100 μs as hit definition time (HDT) and 300 μs for hit lockout time (HLT). The sampling rate for the acoustic emission system was set to 2×10⁶ Hz. A Bessel band

pass filter was used between 20kHz and 800kHz to remove the noise and then digitize the recorded data. The features of acoustic emission hits were extracted in the time domain and frequency domain, among these features weighted peak frequency (WPF) and partial power 1 were selected for pattern recognition due to their confirmed good clustering results [22, 26] [22]. To find the optimum number of clusters *Silhouette* criteria was used and results of various cluster numbers revealed that best separation between clusters appeared for 4 clusters. The K-means function is implemented in MATLAB environment to classify the acoustic emission hits accordingly.

Figure 1 : Schematic of mechanical test samples with location of acoustic emission sensors and strain gauge a) Bending specimen b) Tensile specimen

3 RESULTS

3.1 EFFECT OF LOADING TYPE ON HYBRID EFFECT

Figure 2(a) shows the results of tensile strength, chord modulus and hybrid effect for selected samples from each laminate type. As is seen in Figure 2 hybrid fiber laminates, 1C, 2C, and 3C demonstrated similar mechanical response, i.e. their tensile strength and chord modulus were at the same range. Considering a similar ratio of carbon to glass fibers for these hybrid laminates similarity in mechanical properties is expected. However, 13C hybrid composite shows higher mechanical properties compared to all other hybrid laminates which are due to the higher volume fraction of carbon fibers. The interesting observation about mechanical properties of 13C laminate is that it shows even higher strength compared to nonhybrid AC specimen. This higher strength of 13C laminate can be attributed to the presence of residual compressive stresses due to the difference between thermal expansion coefficient of carbon and glass layers. The 13C laminate can be considered as glass layers sandwiched between two carbon plies. Glass fibers have higher thermal expansion coefficient as compared to carbon fibers, thus the curing process followed by cooling procedure results in compression at carbon layers and tension at glass plies [27]. Since the volume fraction of carbon plies is higher than glass layers net residual stresses inside the 13C laminates become compressive. Therefore, despite lower chord modulus, the tensile strength of the 13C hybrid laminate will be higher than AC sample.

Calculating hybrid effect values for tensile tests shows that 1C, 2C, and 3C samples do not demonstrate very significant differences, therefore it is obvious that the stacking sequence of hybrid laminates does not influence the amount of resultant hybrid effect under tensile loading condition. Despite lower volume fraction of glass fibers in 13C specimen it does not show smaller hybrid effect value, which suggests that for achieving high hybrid effects, the volume fraction of high elongation fiber does not have to be necessarily more than low elongation fibers, i.e. carbon layers.

Figure 2(b) presents the results of flexural strength, flexural modulus and hybrid effect for the specimens with average values as a representative of each laminate type. Comparison between 1C, 2C and 3C laminates which all have similar carbon to glass ratio revealed that their value of hybrid effect increased as the low elongation plies were closer to the neutral axis of flexural specimen. This

observation showed that the stacking sequence has a significant influence on the flexural behavior of hybrid laminates. On the other hand, 13C specimen did not demonstrate as high hybrid effect as 3C laminate. Moreover, 1C laminate revealed a hybrid effect value like 13C sample, therefore indicating that carbon plies at the surface of flexural laminate can prevent the achievement of considerable hybrid effects under flexural loading condition.

Figure 2 : a) Tensile Test b) Flexural Test

3.2 ACOUSTIC EMISSION ANALYSIS

Clustering the acoustic emission data for all laminates revealed similar results, therefore the results of the only 1C sample are shown in Figure 3. Figure 3a and 3c show the plot of Partial power 1 vs Weighted peak frequency for bending and tensile samples with 1C configuration[26]. It is obvious that the number of acoustic emission hits appearing under tensile test were more than the number obtained under flexural loading condition. This difference is attributed to the bigger volume of material exposed to loading during the tensile test as compared to bending sample, hence resulting in higher damage susceptibility of laminate under the same stress levels. Moreover, at weighted peak frequency between 300-400 kHz no acoustic emission activity is observed for most of the bending specimens while this region shows significant acoustic emission hits for all tensile samples. Since source of acoustic emission hits are the damages that happen in material, the absence of a certain range of acoustic emission hits implies rareness of a certain failure type under bending load conditions.

Figure 3b and 3d show the results of clustering with K-means algorithm for acoustic emission activity. The results of clustering show four distinct classes with ranges between, 50-160 kHz, 150-300 kHz, 300-400kHz and 400-600 kHz. The lowest frequency range is attributed to matrix cracking while the cluster with the highest range is related to fiber breakage [19, 26]. These attributions are directly relevant to the stiffness of material that is being damaged, in other words, materials with higher stiffness result in an acoustic emission with higher frequencies. The middle range is due to damages occurring at the interface of matrix and fibers, i.e. debonding or delamination. The other type of interface damage

that is present in tensile tests due to uniaxial loading at fiber direction is fiber pullout. This damage is not very common in flexural loading conditions due to inherent load profile, therefore it can happen only if the tension at the bottom layer of bending sample exceeds the energy required for fiber pull out. Thus, the cluster of acoustic emission hits between 300-400 kHz is related to fiber pull out which is observed in significant number under tensile loading condition.

Figure 3: a) Unclustered Acoustic Emission data for bending sample of 1C laminate b) Clustering result for bending sample of 1C Laminate c) Unclustered Acoustic Emission data for Tensile sample of 1C hybrid laminate d) Clustering result for Tensile sample of 1C Laminate

To further analyze the hits obtained through clustering and distinguish their characteristics, Short-Time Fast Fourier Transformation (*STFFT*) function is applied to get the 3D waterfall *spectrogram* of a sample hit waveforms from each cluster as seen in Figure 4. The transformation is calculated using a *Hanning* Window size of 64 utilizing 30 overlap points and 1000 frequency points to calculate Discrete Fourier Transformation. Figure 4a shows the spectrogram of a sample hit from the cluster attributed to matrix cracking. This spectrogram shows a single peak in power at the frequency of about 0.7MHz, therefore presenting that the energy of waveform is concentrated at low frequencies. Absence of energy concentration at higher frequencies implies low stiffness of material being damaged, hence demonstrating lower stresses required for damage growth. Figure 4b illustrates a sample spectrogram from the second cluster with weighted peak frequency range of 150-300kHz. It is seen that unlike matrix cracking the energy of acoustic emission wave due to interface failure is distributed between 0.2 to 0.5 MHz. The highest power value is at 0.2MHz and a small peak is present around 0.4MHz, therefore

indicating the complexity of failure mechanism. This distribution in peak power values can be attributed to the involvement of two material types, i.e. matrix and fiber during interface failure. Figure 4c presents spectrogram for damages attributed to fiber pull out. It is seen that the energy of waveform is spread out from 0.1MHz to 1MHz with a main concentration between 0.1MHz and 0.6MHz. Moreover, the fluctuations start very early in time domain compared to other damage types, therefore indicating high resistance for the propagation of this damage inside the laminate. This observation is expected since high continuous friction between fiber and matrix material is expected when fiber pull outs occur. Previous studies have also indicated that phenomena related to friction result in continuous spectrograms over both time and frequency range, as compared to typical crack or impact signals [28]. Figure 4d shows the spectrogram related to a sample hit from fiber breakage cluster. It is seen that the main energy concentration is between 0.4 and 0.6 MHz. This small energy peak at a very tight range is like the behavior observed at first cluster, therefore indicating the contribution of a single material type during failure propagation. However, due to the higher frequency of this significant peak, high stiffness of failed material is implied i.e. fiber failure. Overall spectrograms obtained from different clusters represent the specific source of the damage attributed to that class of acoustic emission hits. Further analysis of spectrograms for similar failure types under flexural and tensile loading revealed no major differences in the frequency-time structure of results, therefore the type of load did not influence the acoustic emission waveforms.

Figure 4: Sample Spectrograms of a) Matrix Cracking b) Interface Failure c)Fiber Pull out d)Fiber Breakage

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a unidirectional CFRP and 4 different configurations of unidirectional glass/carbon fiber hybrid laminates are produced through VARTM method and mechanically tested under tensile and flexural loading conditions according to standards. Stacking sequence had a significant effect on the hybrid effect value under flexural loading while its effect under tensile loading condition was negligible. It is seen that the highest hybrid effects are obtained for flexural specimens when their low elongation

plies are in the middle layers of the sample, i.e. sample 3C. Although the lower ratio of carbon to glass plies results in a reduction of tensile elastic modulus, it does not necessarily increase hybrid effect value as in the case of 13C laminate; which had similar hybrid effect amount as 2C specimen. Despite the lowest hybrid effect under tensile loading, specimen 3C possessed the highest hybrid effect under flexural loading, therefore, showing different behavior of the same hybrid laminate under various conditions.

Results of acoustic emission are clustered into 4 clusters for all samples and each class of acoustic emission hit is attributed to a different damage type, namely, Matrix cracking, Interface failure, Fiber pull out and Fiber breakage. The cluster related to fiber pull-out is not present for flexural tests which is due to the rareness of this damage under bending load conditions. The spectrograms of sample hits from each cluster are obtained and frequency-time structure of each hit is analyzed. It is seen that for damage type in which a single composite constituent fails, the energy of the wave is concentrated in a narrow frequency region for a short period of time. On the other hand, for failure types that consist of two material types involved, i.e. interface failure and fiber pull-out, the structure of spectrogram shows energy spread through a wider frequency spectrum and for a longer time period. Specifically, the spectrogram of the hits related to fiber pull out show stretched energy peaks over the frequency range which is possibly due to inherent friction of this damage type.

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